

THE ANDREW WILLIAMSON COLLECTION.

The collection is comprised mostly of ceramic material acquired in the course of two surveys and two small excavations carried out by Williamson in southern Iran from 1968 to 1971. The surveys were carried out along the Persian Gulf coast from Jāsk to Qālāt and included the major islands and inland south of a line from Zabol to Shiraz to cover the routes from Istakhr and Shiraz to Sirjan and Bam, Persian Seistan, and the Kur river plain. The excavated material comes from two sites, Sirjan, excavated under the auspices of the Siraf project in 1970, and Tepe Dasht-i-Deh excavated as part of the Tepe Yahya project in 1970 and 1971.

The material is currently stored in The Ruskin Gallery and occupies a series of drawers, packing cases and sacks, about 150 in all. During the last three weeks ~~that~~ ~~I have been working on the material~~, I have examined the contents of all of them to see what the collection is made up of and how it is organised. So far I have been able to list the material as it stands and have given each container a new number which is to be found circled at the top left hand corner of any box or crate and written on a piece of cardboard inserted into sacks and bags. These numbers are to be found in two notebooks which list in detail the provenance of every sherd in that container and where a broad dating for the material is not self evident, which excludes most of the glazed wares and the published Sassanian groups, have given my own ideas about it. All of the material appears to be either Sassanian or Islamic, *but* mostly Islamic.

The survey material has generally been divided into the following types:

Glazed wares-slip painted, sgraffiato, frit wares and so on.

Far eastern wares-Celadons, blue and white, stone wares etc.

Sassanian types-Pedestals, painted wares, brittle wares etc.

Moulded wares.

Plain wares-generally divided by form, fabric or relative size, Sassanian or Islamic.

~~Some sites and groups of sites have not however been divided up in this manner.~~

Where a surveyed area seems to present a homogeneous geographical or cultural unit, i.e. The Bushehr Peninsula or the Minab Delta, H and K respectively, material has been divided within that framework i.e. Sgraffiato from K, or Fine Orange Wares from H. At the moment then, if one wanted to find out what types of wares had been found in, say, a survey of Hormuz Island, ~~one would find the appropriate letter for that part of the coast and then examine the cards and hope that the particular site that you were interested in would be mentioned by name. This is not very often the case~~ *where one would find a list of ~~the~~ types that had been found there.*

The excavated material on the other hand has not been divided into types but has been kept in its archaeological context. Thus we have SS-Sirjan, SS- Sirjan survey or surface A-G letters in triangles which represent trenches. and numbers in circles which represent the relationship of stratified deposits to each other which is given more specifically on the section drawings. Where ~~contiguous trenches have a~~ layers are obviously the same but have acquired different numbers because of baulks et they have been put together by Williamson. Typically, because of the difficulty of numbering large quantities of featured sherds, the numbering conventions have very often been dropped so that one may have a group of sherds numbered B19, which will correspond to survey material from a site near Bandar I Lengeh. Usually one can tell which is meant, but it would present a problem for somebody approaching it without knowing the pitfalls.

Another problem with the Sirjan material is that about 20% comes from surveys carried out on the surface of the 2 x 2.5 km site. Unfortunately, no map giving the location of these areas to the citadel and the trenches has yet been located, although a plan of the citadel does exist. One hopes that this will come to light eventually

Keep the Sirjan types have already been published and are kept in specific drawers but the information about the presence of these and other material needs to be made more is

Intelligible, the survey material useful way of organizing it rather than by site. Williamson had begun to do this. However

accessable
 the publication of those types would be an ideal way of making the collection collected and the organization of the collection into a new series of types, and Many new types have come to light in the Gulf area since this material was has been found on any site, but this information at the moment is quite inadequate. itself, AA. The cards should also provide a clue themselves to the kind of pottery which for more remote sites. This is not the case for Hormuz Island which has a section to properly by referring to the notebooks where theodolite and other readings are given as many of the sites surveyed are too small to have names, and can only be located *material on now* locating the material in the drawers in the collection would be more difficult at the moment. An organization of the collection by type would be the next and to find all the material on now